

Why the End User Community matters

Based on the principle of co-creation, the *RethinkAction* project continuously expands its network and encourages citizens (society), decision makers (policy) and stakeholders (economy) to become active agents and collaborators. The End User Community is vital to the success of the *RethinkAction* project since engagement and participation fundamentally define the outcome of the platform.

What can end-users expect from RethinkAction?

- Land use-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS) catalogued at local, EU and global scales.
- High-resolution climate data and land use maps that visualise climate change impacts and risks in each case study.
- A multiscale evaluation framework that simulates:
 - 1) Future scenarios consistent across scales.
 - 2) Local system dynamic models for the integrated assessment of solutions.
 - 3) An upscaling function for solutions to EU and global scales (WILIAM IAM).

Interested? Engage!

Is your region facing climatic challenges and are you interested in exploring Land use-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS)? Then sign up to become a member of the End User Community.

By signing up, you will not only receive invitations to events and opportunities relating to the project, but also gain access to the Europe- and world-wide network of stakeholders actively contributing to developing the platform to address local and global challenges.

Help to make high-level information on land use and climate change more accessible to people's lives. Join our End User Community to:

- Help to shape the direction in which *RethinkAction* is to be further developed.
- Expand and internationalise your professional network.
- Receive exclusive invitations to work meetings, training sessions and conferences organised by the project consortium.

You want to know more about the *RethinkAction* project?

Visit our website: www.rethinkaction.eu

And follow us on social media: [@rethinkaction](https://www.instagram.com/rethinkaction)

Sign up here:

Or visit: www.rethinkaction.eu/#engage

SCAN ME

A platform to support local land-use decision making.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037104.

About

RethinkAction is funded under the Horizon 2020 Programme (GA No 101037104). The project brings together thirteen partners from nine countries, combining various fields of expertise such as social sciences, political science, land use-based policy, environmental sciences, atmospheric sciences, ICT modelling, integrated assessment modelling, earth observation, climatology and communication.

Objective

The main objective of *RethinkAction* is to engage citizens, stakeholders and decision-makers to participate in land use-based transformation and actively support climate adaptation and mitigation. Six representative case studies based in Europe form the backbone of the *RethinkAction* project. In order to upscale our findings to EU and global levels, the case studies were selected to represent the diversity of climate zones occurring worldwide. Together with our End User Community we are creating an Integrated Assessment Platform which will empower citizens, stakeholders, and decision-makers to analyse climate change and incorporate climate action into the land use policies that will affect our lives in the coming decades.

Why land use?

Land provides the basis for human livelihoods and well-being including being a supplier of food, freshwater and multiple other ecosystem services, as well as biodiversity. Land is both a source and a sink of greenhouse gases and plays a key role in the exchange of energy, water and aerosols between the land surface and atmosphere. Land ecosystems and biodiversity are vulnerable to ongoing climate change, as well as weather and climate extremes, to different extents. Sustainable land management can contribute to reducing the negative impacts of multiple stressors, including climate change, on ecosystems and societies.

Source: IPCC Special Report on Climate Change and Land, 2019

How does the Integrated Assessment Platform benefit stakeholders?

The user-friendly Integrated Assessment Platform will deliver clear and valuable information on climate change and increase general awareness of Land use-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS). Moreover, it will allow users to access LAMS linking local, European and global scales based on the six representative case studies. Within this approach, *RethinkAction* aims to create an understanding for political and societal changes. By developing solutions through participatory processes, the project also promotes active participation in climate action by decision-makers, stakeholders and citizens in Europe.

Land use-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS) catalogue

The LAMS catalogue will be integrated in the platform; it combines a set of 60 solutions across different sectors that are directly related to land use. These include: Agriculture, forestry, energy, urban development, water management and more.

The catalogue helps end users to make informed decisions on positive land use changes that directly respond to their local climate challenges: How can farmers adapt their practices to the changing precipitation patterns in their regions? Which renewable energy technologies can regions apply to mitigate emissions and reach local energy independence? What can citizens do to reduce their impact on climate change?

Analysis at local level

The *RethinkAction* project focuses on regions at NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 levels. After an initial regional problem analysis, the platform allows users to understand the most relevant risks based on essential hazards coming from the main climate change variables.

The problem analysis lays the basis on which the feasibility of the LAMS can be tested in the LAMS Catalogue Explorer for each region in terms of applicability, understanding and priorities.

In a third step, local system dynamic simulation models can play out different policy action scenarios to foresee results on the impacts of LAMS across the sectors (e.g., environment, society, economy, etc.).

This will help end users to:

- Understand the context in their area and detect main climate risks (create awareness).
- Test the applicability of LAMS and understand their characteristics.
- Calculate benefits and opportunities of the solutions: impacts of the application of LAMS in the selected region before their implementation.

Analysis at EU / Global level

The LAMS assessed at local level can also be applied at EU / global level by upscaling through a simulation with a system dynamics Integrated Assessment Model [WILIAM].

This will help to:

- Design and evaluate the impacts of land-based policies at EU and global scale.
- Foster local action and collaborative action.
- Understand the consequences of inaction and delayed action.

What would happen if the LAMS were assessed at local level ...

Simulation with system dynamics integrated assessment model [WILIAM]

Upscaling solutions

... would be applied at EU/global level in all feasible locations?

